

A hydrometer

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Abstract: Here, I construct a simple, elegant hydrometer model measuring the fluid exit from an outlet in the triangular reservoir or a mountain lake. This two-parameter hydro-mechanical system is based on some dynamically justified physical principles for energy dissipations through the discharge coefficient and the complementary friction. It is expressed as a simple differential equation whose exact-analytical solutions have been presented. The new model is an extension to the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-law, however, it differs fundamentally from the classical law. As the fluid surface area evolves with the hydraulic head, this becomes the game-changer characterizing the hydrometer. For technical use, the model provides the hydrometer and the hydrometer-velocity measuring the evolving depth of the frictional fluid and its exit velocity. Analytical solutions are constructed for the hydrometer for contrasting scenarios: without and with narrow conduit approximation, and dam collapse, resulting in completely different dynamics. I showed that a hypergeometric function analytically solves the full hydrometer. The pleasing compact dam collapse model possesses an exact analytical solution. Although structurally drastically simplified, the dam collapse solution appears plausible. As a whole, the hypergeometric solution for narrow exit without approximation and the dam collapse solution behave similarly with strong non-linearity for both the hydrometer and the hydrometer-velocity. The results for conduit approximation are fundamentally different than those for the dam collapse and the hypergeometric solution. I proved that the model approximation loses the fundamental physical essence of the hydrometer resulting in paradoxically invalid solution. Contrary to the prevailing perception, the hydrometer is critical to the reservoir free-surface kinetic energy. The crucial revelation is that hydro-mechanically, this kinetic energy provides a vital ingredient to the system that cannot just be ignored; if done so, it destroys the physical system. This is a paradigm-shift in hydro-mechanics. The new hydrometer can be applied to different engineering and environmental problems, including the draining and emergency evacuation of the glacial or mountain lakes, hydropower reservoirs, and the fluid vessels; and their engineered discharges. For mountain flash flood simulation, my method provides cost-effective, efficient and probably the best analytical solutions with the initial hydrographs.

1 Introduction

The draining and emptying of mountain lakes and reservoirs, and fluid vessels (tankers) is an important hydro-mechanical problem for environmental, civil and hydraulic engineers while operating hydropower plants, irrigation systems, flood control and decommissioning of endangered structures, and the loading and un-loading of fluid (e.g., oil) tankers. Following one of the most important contributions by Torricelli (1644) and Bernoulli (1738) in hydraulics, their seminal analytical models and solutions for the cylindrical and rectangular vessels have been widely applied and improved over time (de Oliveira et al., 2000; Lin et al., 2008; Maranni et al., 2021; Malcherek, 2022). However, there exists no analytical model to describe the draining of a general triangular wedge-type fluid-body with any frictional property. These are other spectrum of the hydro-mechanical problems with application potential.

Here, I construct a novel physical-mathematical model addressing this standing problem by presenting a simple analytical and the most efficient and cost-effective method with a hydrometer. My method provides the quickest estimate of the enormous forces carried by the exit jets with potential catastrophic consequences downstream.

It also furnishes the first analytical solution for the controlled evacuation of the fluid from a triangular-reservoir through the sluice gate, or the partial or full collapse of the reservoir dam. The solution demonstrates that the hydrometer stage decreases rapidly as the exit gate operates. Towards the end, the discharge rate is very slow, finally completing the evacuation process. These behaviours are in-line with our intuition. However, I showed that simplifying the inherently complex hydro-mechanical system with a narrow conduit approximation adversely results in severe consequences, destroying the structure and the physical essence of the hydrometer. This suggests that one must be very careful in approximating a differential equation representing a critical mechanical system for the sake of technical simplicity.

The general results presented here indicate the application potential of the new hydrometer in the relevant environmental, civil, hydraulic and engineering, and the earth system sciences. For mountain flash flood and tsunami simulations (Mergili et al., 2018; 2020; Pudasaini and Mergili, 2019; Sattar et al., 2025), the new method yields the most cost-efficient and the best analytical solutions for the initial conditions with the hydrograph and the incipient velocity at the dam location (Baselt et al., 2021).

2 The model

Consider a triangular-shaped fluid body (reservoir), say in a mountain valley, with slope ζ , fluid depth h , width W_T at the top free-surface, and the length L . Also consider an outlet (conduit) with depth H and width W_A at the base (the front face) of the reservoir. Moreover, let ρ be the density of the fluid in the reservoir and g the gravitational acceleration. Assume that, as the outlet operates, the mass exits (outflows) the reservoir with the velocity u_A (the outflow speed, or the discharge velocity) and the fluid at the free surface moves (lowers down) with the velocity u_T . Also assume that μ_c represents the overall (internal and the boundary) material friction, generally a small positive number. The friction μ_c includes: (i) the internal friction due to the motion and deformation of the mobile (three-dimensional) tubing-type (channel) sub-body in the reservoir, (ii) the friction of this mobile tunneling-body against the contemporary immobile surrounding complementary material, and (ii) when the mobile material encounters the reservoir (vessel) boundary, inducing the boundary friction. Then, considering the kinetic energy, potential energy and the frictional energy loss, the energy balance takes the form:

$$\frac{1}{2}\rho u_T^2 + \lambda \rho g h = \frac{1}{2}\rho u_A^2 + \lambda \rho g h \mu_c, \quad \text{or,} \quad u_T^2 + 2\lambda g h \mu_p = u_A^2, \quad (1)$$

where, $\mu_p = 1 - \mu_c$ is the effective system friction coefficient, or the complementary friction coefficient. Practically, the parameter λ mostly takes value 1 or 1/2. This will become clearer later. Sometimes, a constant height h_f (a substantial quantity) is subtracted from the actual fluid height h while considering the potential energy by expressing the energy loss in friction as $-\rho g h_f$, where $h_f < h$ is a friction constant (de Oliveira et al., 2000). Yet, others also even simply reduce the gravity by a significant amount (du Buat, 1786). However, my approach of frictional energy loss appears to be dynamically better justified as it evolves with the actual material load.

The conservation of mass implies

$$u_T A_T = u_A A_A, \quad (2)$$

where u_A is the bulk outflow velocity (efflux). With the aperture friction μ_A (Bernoulli, 1738) and the length of the triangular reservoir $L = \cot(\zeta)h$, the fluid surface area and the conduit area are given by:

$$A_T = \cot(\zeta)h W_T, \quad A_A = H W_A \mu_A. \quad (3)$$

This means, A_T is decreasing linearly with h , in contrast to the cylindrical and rectangular reservoir for which A_T remains constant. μ_A is the empirical outflow coefficient, or contraction ratio of the jet behind the orifice (Bernoulli, 1738; Liu et al., 2008). In principle, μ_A may be modelled in different ways. This can take a different form when the momentum balance also considers the reaction force from the fluid base (Malcherek, 2022).

It is important to note that, in contrast to the classical problems, where the fluid surface area remains constant because of the consideration of the cylindrical or a rectangular vessel (Torricelli, 1644; Bernoulli, 1738; de Oliveira et al., 2000; Lin et al., 2008; Maranni et al., 2021), in the present setting, the fluid surface area evolves with the hydraulic head at the outlet. As will be clearer later, this plays a crucial role in the description of the hydrometer of interest here.

Now, combining (1)-(3), after simplification, I obtain an expression for the exit (discharge) velocity u_A as:

$$u_A = h \sqrt{\frac{2\lambda gh\mu_p}{h^2 - \left[H \tan(\zeta) \frac{W_A}{W_T} \mu_A \right]^2}}. \quad (4)$$

This provides a relationship between the discharge velocity and the hydraulic head, h at the dam. This is an extension to the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-law (Torricelli, 1644; Bernoulli, 1738; Malcherek, 2022). The appearance of h in the front numerator and h^2 in the denominator with $h^2 - \alpha^2$ on the right hand side of (4) becomes the game-changer as both emerge due to the dynamically changing fluid surface area with fluid depth at the dam. These would otherwise be unity with the cylindrical or the rectangular vessels or reservoirs in Torricelli-Bernoulli-type-laws, with 1 in place of $H \tan(\zeta)$. The Torricelli principle corresponds to the most simple situation: $W_A \ll W_T$, which simply says that the outflow velocity u_A from the reservoir (vessel) outlet is the free fall velocity. This is equivalent to neglecting the terms in the square brackets in (4) and setting $\lambda = 1, \mu_p = 1$ in the numerator, which effectively means no frictional consideration.

Next, I derive an evolution equation for the hydraulic head at the dam. This requires the actual information on the reservoir fluid volume, which, with (3), is given by:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} L h W_T = \frac{1}{2} [\cot(\zeta) h] h W_T. \quad (5)$$

This shows that, the fluid surface area decreases as the mass drains out through the outlet (orifice). This is a fundamentally different situation as compared to the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-type models in which the surface area remains constant (Torricelli, 1644; Bernoulli, 1738; Malcherek, 2022; de Oliveira et al., 2000; Lin et al., 2008; Maranni et al., 2021). This is a game-changer.

The reduction of the fluid height h in the reservoir (vessel) is described by the mass balance. As the rate of change of the reservoir fluid volume and the volume flux through the exit balance, we have:

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = -A_A u_A \mu_A. \quad (6)$$

This essentially means that the rate by which the mass in the reservoir decreases is exactly balanced by the mass that flows out through the orifice (outlet).

From (5), it is evident that the change in volume is proportional to the change in the fluid depth with the proportionality being the function of the fluid depth, i.e., $dV/dt = [\cot(\zeta) W_T h] dh/dt$. This is in contrast to the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli cylindrical or rectangular reservoir problem for which the proportionality factor is a constant, namely the sectional area of the vessel. These special features characterize the hydro-mechanics of the triangular reservoir. Additionally, the rate dV/dt also depends on the reservoir width and the slope of the bathymetry with the rate (behaviour) transition at $\zeta = 45^\circ$.

The hydrometer

Expressions (3), (4) and (5) inserting into (6), after simplification, results in a simple, elegant model:

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = -\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\beta h}{h^2 - \alpha^2}}, \quad (7)$$

which is the descent velocity of the fluid surface, where, $\alpha = H \tan(\zeta) \mu_A \frac{W_A}{W_T}, \beta = 2\lambda g \mu_p$. This is a two-parameter hydro-mechanical system. The only two physical parameters are the vena contracta μ_A , or the

discharge coefficient $A_C = A_A \mu_A$ (Bernoulli, 1738), and the overall (internal and boundary) complementary friction μ_p . The model (7) differs fundamentally from the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-law, as there emerges h^2 in the denominator on its right hand side, and also because in Torricelli-Bernoulli-law there appears 1 in place of $H \tan(\zeta)$ in α with adjusted area ratio to width ratio, and $\mu_p = 1, \lambda = 1$ in β . These are the special features that characterize (7).

I call (7) the hydrometer. This is based on some physical principles. It is fascinating to observe the emergence of α both in the numerator and the denominator on the right-hand-side of (7) with the h^2 therein. This resulted due to the physical setting of the reservoir problem considered here. Below, I discuss three scenarios to apply (7) in solving technical problems.

2.1 The full hydrometer problem

The model (7) can be viewed in different ways. Analytical solutions can be constructed for (7) for contrasting scenarios, including the small and large outlet conduits or, the sluice gates without and with some approximations, and dam collapse, resulting in completely different dynamics. I present the full solution in its native form (without any reduction) in Section 3.1.

2.2 The small outlet approximation

For a given small outlet area, as α can be a small number as compared to the fluid depth h at the dam, one may apply the approximation $h^2 - \alpha^2 \approx h^2$. Then, (7) reduces to

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = -\frac{\gamma}{\sqrt{h}}, \quad (8)$$

with $\gamma = \alpha\sqrt{\beta}$, where $\alpha = H \tan(\zeta)\mu_A \frac{W_A}{W_T}, \beta = 2g\mu_p$. Importantly, because the outlet is so narrow, virtually there is no difference in pressure at the top and the bottom of the outlet. So, $\lambda = 1$ is a legitimate choice for this situation that is implemented in β . However, as will be clearer later, such a model reduction that may be considered in engineering practice, can be mathematically-physically invalid. The small outlet approximation solutions are presented in Section 3.2

2.3 The dam collapse

It is important to realise that, as the dam collapses (partially, $W_A < W_T$; or the entire width, $W_A \approx W_T$), the outlet height evolves with the fluid height in the water-body, which means $H \approx h$. However, for this, the discharge velocity is the out-flow section-averaged velocity, or simply the velocity at the middle-height of the fluid exit. Moreover, the potential energy differs at the top and the bottom of the fluid exit. This variation can be taken into account by considering the mean of the material load (or the potential energy) at the bottom (ρgh) and the top (0), i.e., $(1/2)\rho gh$. This is achieved by setting $\lambda = 1/2$ in β . Yet, note that the formal derivation by integrating the potential energy through the exit depth may lead to the same result as that by simply considering $\lambda = 1/2$. With this, and the new definition of $\alpha = \tan(\zeta)\mu_A \frac{W_A}{W_T}$ and $\beta = g\mu_p$, (7) reduces to:

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = -\alpha\sqrt{\frac{\beta h}{1 - \alpha^2}}. \quad (9)$$

As such, (9) can now be re-written in a compact form with a single collective-parameter $\gamma = \alpha\sqrt{\frac{\beta}{1 - \alpha^2}}$:

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = -\gamma\sqrt{h}. \quad (10)$$

Structurally, (10) is pleasing and takes the form of the Torricelli-Bernoulli-equation, yet, dynamically quite different, also because it contains different essential hydro-mechanical parameters involved in γ through α and β that emerge due to the consideration of wedged-reservoir and different energy dissipation mechanisms mentioned earlier. Solutions for the dam collapse scenario are presented in Section 3.3

Figure 1: The full Euler-P hypergeometric solution for the triangular dam with small conduit: A. the hydrometer given by (12), B. the hydrometer-velocity given by (14).

3 The solutions

3.1 The full Euler-P hypergeometric solution

To proceed, differentiate (7) with respect to time, yielding:

$$2 [h^2 - \alpha^2]^2 \sqrt{h} \frac{d^2h}{dt^2} + \alpha \sqrt{\beta} [h^2 + \alpha^2] \sqrt{h^2 - \alpha^2} \frac{dh}{dt} = 0. \quad (11)$$

This is a second order ordinary differential equation with three singular points, namely, $h = \pm \alpha, 0$. So, there exists a hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1^P$ (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1972; Olde Daalhuis, 2010) that exactly solves the hydrometer (7) analytically. The solution in its fascinating, elegant form reads:

$$t = -2i \frac{h_0}{\sqrt{\beta}} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{h_0}} {}_2F_1^P \left[-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{4}; \frac{5}{4}; \frac{h_0^2}{\alpha^2} \right] - \frac{1}{\sqrt{h}} {}_2F_1^P \left[-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{4}; \frac{5}{4}; \frac{h^2}{\alpha^2} \right] \right], \quad (12)$$

where, i is an imaginary number, and h_0 is the fluid depth at the initial time, $t = 0$. This constitutes and proves a prime theorem, called the P-Theorem:

The P-Theorem: *A hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1^P$ as in (12) solves the hydrometer (7).*

With this, (7) is termed as the Euler-P hypergeometric differential equation. The time the reservoir is fully drained, t_d , which happens as $h \rightarrow 0$ in (12), and is given by:

$$t_d = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} -2i \frac{h_0}{\sqrt{\beta}} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{h_0}} {}_2F_1^P \left[-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{4}; \frac{5}{4}; \frac{h_0^2}{\alpha^2} \right] - \frac{1}{\sqrt{h}} {}_2F_1^P \left[-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{4}; \frac{5}{4}; \frac{h^2}{\alpha^2} \right] \right], \quad (13)$$

providing important solutions for quick engineering practice for the fluid drainage. With (12) at hand, employing (4), the hydrometer-velocity (u_A), and hydrometer-flux (Q); per unit width; are obtained analytically:

$$u_A = h \sqrt{\frac{\beta h}{h^2 - \alpha^2}}, \quad Q = h u_A. \quad (14)$$

The full Euler-P hypergeometric solution is presented in Fig. 1. The parameter values are chosen with practical views as: $g = 9.81$, $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $h_0 = 1.5$, $W_T = 1.0$, $W_A = 0.15$, $H = 0.15$, $\mu_p = 0.6$, $\mu_A = 0.65$.

Approximate solution with $\alpha^2 \rightarrow 0$

In engineering practice, often incredibly small terms are neglected in relation to other terms in the underlying

Figure 2: The Euler-P hypergeometric solution approximation ($h^2 - \alpha^2 \approx h^2$) to the hydrometer for the triangular dam given by (12) for different safety control parameters s_p .

expression. For small outlet, α is a very small number. So, it is logical to think to ignore α^2 in the denominator of (7). One way to do this is multiply α^2 by a number s_p (call it the safety parameter) constituting $s_p\alpha^2$, and successively decrease its value from 1 towards 0 and analyze the solution behaviour with (12) hoping that the solutions would converge to some reference state. The results are presented in Fig. 2. From the physical standpoint, it clearly demonstrates that such an approximation is paradoxically invalid as the solution diverges to time infinity as $s_p\alpha^2 \rightarrow 0$. However, note that, $s_p\alpha^2 \rightarrow 0$ does not mean that the sluice gate is infinitely small (narrow), because, not α also occurring in the numerator of (7) is reduced, but α^2 that appears in the denominator in $h^2 - \alpha^2$ in (7) is reduced while employing the Euler-P hypergeometric solution (12). This strange behaviour is discussed further with some other simplified solutions at Section 4.3.

3.2 The small outlet approximation

Exact, analytical solution to the model (8) associated with the direct outlet approximation exists, and reads:

$$h = \left[h_0^{3/2} - \frac{3}{2}\gamma t \right]^{2/3}. \quad (15)$$

From (15), one obtains the discharge time:

$$t = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[h_0^{3/2} - h^{3/2} \right], \quad (16)$$

and thus, the time the reservoir is fully drained, t_d (as $h \rightarrow 0$):

$$t_d = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{\gamma} h_0^{3/2}. \quad (17)$$

With (15), the hydrometer-velocity (u_A) and the hydrometer-flux (Q) are obtained:

$$u_A = \sqrt{\beta}\sqrt{h}, \quad Q = hu_A. \quad (18)$$

The solutions for the hydrometer and hydrometer-velocity for the narrow conduit approximation model (8) are presented in Fig. 3. The parameter values are chosen as: $g = 9.81$, $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $h_0 = 1.5$, $W_T = 1.0$, $W_A = 0.15$, $H = 0.15$, $\mu_p = 0.6$, $\mu_A = 0.65$.

Figure 3: A: The hydrometer for the narrow conduit approximation in the triangular dam given by (15). B: The corresponding hydrometer-velocity given by (18).

3.3 The dam collapse

The compact model (10) for the dam collapse possesses an exact, analytical solution for the hydrometer h :

$$h = \left[\frac{\gamma}{2}t - \sqrt{h_0} \right]^2. \quad (19)$$

From (19), one obtains the discharge time:

$$t = \frac{2}{\gamma} \left[\sqrt{h} + \sqrt{h_0} \right], \quad (20)$$

and thus, the time the reservoir is fully drained, t_d , which happens as $h \rightarrow 0$:

$$t_d = \frac{2}{\gamma} \sqrt{h_0}. \quad (21)$$

These are practically important engineering information. With (19) at hand, the hydrometer-velocity (u_A) and the hydrometer-flux (Q) are obtained analytically as:

$$u_A = \frac{\gamma}{\alpha} \sqrt{h}, \quad Q = hu_A. \quad (22)$$

The solutions for the hydrometer and hydrometer-velocity for the dam collapse are presented in Fig. 4. The parameter values are chosen as: $g = 9.81$, $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $h_0 = 1.5$, $W_T = 1.0$, $W_A = 0.15$, $\mu_p = 0.6$, $\mu_A = 0.65$.

4 Results and discussion

The result for the narrow conduit exit approximation shown in Fig. 3 associated with (15) is fundamentally different than those presented in Fig. 4 for the dam collapse described by (19) and the full Euler-p hypergeometric solution displayed in Fig. 1 corresponding to the hydrometer (12).

4.1 The full Euler-P hypergeometric solution

As the exit gate operates, the hydrometer stage decreases rapidly, the emptying process continues (Fig. 1A). Towards the end, the rate is very slow, finally approaching the null state, completing the evacuation process. As a whole, for the full Euler-P hypergeometric solution for narrow exit without any approximation, the dynamics

Figure 4: A: The hydrometer for the triangular dam collapse given by (19). B: The corresponding hydrometer-velocity given by (22).

is non-linear. The hydrometer-velocity, however, exhibits a completely different behaviour (Fig. 1B). In the inception of the mass release, the exit velocity decreases slowly from its maximum initial value. Somewhere in the middle of the draining process, the rate of velocity drop amplifies, and in the final stage of the expulsion, the velocity jumps down to quickly attain the null value as the process of mass exit comes to an end. So, dynamically, the hydrometer and the hydrometer-velocity display completely different behaviour.

4.2 The small outlet approximation

The curiosity now is the exit dynamics with the narrow outlet approximation, Fig. 3. For this, after the opening of the gate, the hydrometer first drops slowly, continues that way, and close to the end of the fluid draining, the rate of decrease of the hydraulic head is rapid as the reservoir is emptied. This is a completely different situation compared with Fig. 1, and counter intuitive, also as compared with the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-law. Perhaps, there exists such situations in nature. This requires further study. However, the narrow conduit approximation hydrometer-velocity in Fig. 3 somehow shows qualitatively similar dynamics as that for the Euler-P hypergeometric solution for the narrow exit and the dam collapse.

4.3 Is the approximation $h^2 - \alpha^2 \approx h^2$ valid?

Comparing Fig. 3 with Fig. 1, it becomes clear that though technically the approximation $h^2 - \alpha^2 \approx h^2$ drastically simplifies the mathematical complexity, the reduced model (8) loses the fundamental physical essence of the hydrometer. The point is, as the flow begins, α^2 always possesses substantial to commanding control over h^2 , no matter what. The origin of α^2 in $h^2 - \alpha^2$ lies on the important hydro-mechanical process in including the essential kinetic energy of the system at the top of the reservoir. The crucial revelation here is that, structurally, and hydro-mechanically, this kinetic energy provides the vital ingredient to the system that cannot just be ignored. If done so, that destroys the physical system under consideration, as I have shown this.

However, this does not happen to the classical Bernoulli-Torricelli problem, for which, whether the free-surface kinetic energy is included (Bernoulli, 1738) or not (Torricelli, 1644), the quality of the system, or the solution, remains unchanged. The question is only its quantitative picture. However, for the new hydrometer for the triangular reservoir emptying process, neglecting the important component, the kinetic energy associated with the motion of the free surface, completely changes the characteristic behaviour of the system and the quality of its solution. This is a paradigm-shift in hydro-mechanics. This proves that the hydrometer is critical to the free-surface kinetic energy that fundamentally controls its dynamic behaviour, that is totally in contrast to our prevailing perception of the cylindrical or the rectangular reservoir emptying process.

Figure 5: A: The hydrometer-flux for the Euler-P hypergeometric solution in the triangular dam given by (14). B: The hydrometer-flux for the triangular dam collapse given by (22). C: The hydrometer-flux for the narrow conduit approximation in the triangular dam given by (18).

Although, technically, for small α , one may approximate $h^2 - \alpha^2$ with h^2 simplifying the situation, it adversely results in severe consequences. (I) It destroys the Euler-P hypergeometric differential equation, and thus the key aspect of the hydrometer. (II) As (7) becomes (8), its solution (behaviour) changes completely as it consists of only one singular point (at $h = 0$), and it shatters the hypergeometric structure of the hydrometer. So, this proves that, from the rigorous physical-mathematical point of view, one must be very careful in approximating a differential equation representing a mechanical system for the sake of technical simplicity. I have proven above in Fig. 2 that, even in the limit of $(h^2 - \alpha^2) \rightarrow h^2$, the hypergeometric solution (12) of (7) possesses completely different picture than that produced with the reduced differential equation (8).

4.4 The dam break solution without approximation

Following the structure of the full Euler-P hypergeometric solution in Fig. (1), the dam break solution without approximation presented in Fig. 4 appears plausible. Although from the mathematical point of view the system (10) representing the dam break scenario is drastically reduced, the solution can still be physically valid. This is surprising. Compared to the full hypergeometric solution in Fig. 1, the process of reservoir emptying with the dam collapse is quite rapid. This is physically justified, because, with the dam break, the mass exit is unparallelly fast in relation to the mass exit through the small outlet in Fig. 1.

As the dam collapses, the hydrometer stage decreases rapidly (Fig. 4A). Towards the end, the outflow rate is very slow, finally completing the evacuation process. As a whole, the dynamics is non-linear, qualitatively similar to that for the full Euler-P hypergeometric solution for narrow exit without any approximation.

4.5 The hydrometer-fluxes

The panels A and B in Fig. 1, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 are hydro-dynamically linked. How quickly the fluid is discharged depends on how fast it flows out. This is better described by the hydrometer-flux (Fig. 5) which combines both the flow stage (panels A) and the exit velocity (panels B) in these figures, and thus presents the overall dynamics. Yet, the narrow conduit hydrometer-flux for the approximate model (8) in Fig. 5C displays a linear dynamics against the strongly non-linear decrease for the same for the full Euler-P hypergeometric solution for the narrow exit and the dam collapse. These novel results and their comparisons are surprising.

4.6 The parameter control on the dynamics

For all the settings, variations of the model parameters produce physically and dynamically consistent results. (I) Increasing h_0 and W_T (the reservoir height and width) slow down the fluid expulsion process. (II) Increasing ζ , W_A , H , μ_p , μ_A (the slope of the reservoir base, exit conduit width and height, complementary friction and the discharge coefficient) enhance the process of fluid expulsion.

4.7 Solutions to other analytical reservoirs

The analytical modelling and solution methods presented here can be extended to other technically important reservoir settings. This includes: the reservoirs with the circular, elliptic and the parabolic bathymetric profiles.

5 Summary

A simple, elegant hydrometer model describing the fluid exit from an outlet in a triangular reservoir is presented. For a triangular reservoir, as the fluid surface area evolves with the hydraulic head at the outlet, this becomes the game-changer and characterizes the new hydrometer. This two-parameter hydro-mechanical system is based on some physical principles including different energy dissipation mechanisms described through the discharge coefficient and the complementary friction. My approach of frictional energy loss is dynamically justified as it is aligned with the actual material load. The new model is an extension to the classical Torricelli-Bernoulli-law, however; it differs fundamentally from the classical law.

Analytical solutions are constructed for the hydrometer for three contrasting technical scenarios: conduits without and with some approximations, and dam collapse, resulting in completely different dynamics. I showed that there exists a fascinating and graceful Euler-P hypergeometric function that analytically solves the full hydrometer. Structurally, the compact model for the dam collapse is pleasing as it takes the form of the Torricelli-Bernoulli-equation and possesses an exact analytical solution. As the exit gate operates, the hydrometer stage decreases rapidly, the emptying process continues. Towards the end, the outflow rate is very slow. As a whole, the hypergeometric solution for narrow exit without any approximation and the dam collapse solution behave similarly with strong non-linearity for both the hydrometer and the hydrometer-velocity. The dam collapse solution appears plausible; although structurally drastically reduced, the solution can still be physically valid.

The results for the narrow conduit approximation are fundamentally different than those for the dam collapse and the full hypergeometric solution corresponding to the hydrometer. Though technically the approximation radically simplifies the mathematical complexity, the narrow conduit approximation model loses the fundamental physical essence of the hydrometer. Such an approximation leads to a counter intuitive situation resulting in paradoxically invalid solution. Contrary to the prevailing perception, I proved that, the hydrometer is critical to the free-surface kinetic energy that fundamentally controls its dynamic behavior. The crucial revelation here is that, structurally, and hydro-mechanically, the kinetic energy at the top of the reservoir is the vital component of the system that cannot just be ignored. This is a paradigm-shift in hydro-mechanics. This suggests that one must be very careful in approximating a differential equation representing a critical mechanical system for the sake of technical simplicity.

All models and solutions presented here are novel. The results show the application potential of the new hydrometer in the relevant environmental, civil and hydraulic engineering, and the earth system sciences. However, these results should be scrutinized with laboratory and field experiments (events) by constraining the two mechanical parameters: complementary friction and the conduit contraction. These are genuine hydro-mechanical problems.

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